
BREATHER AND WOBBLE SOLUTIONS FOR THE KONNO-SANUKI EQUATION VIA BÄCKLUND TRANSFORMATION

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Abstract

In this paper, we use the Bäcklund transformations to construct the breather and wobble exact solutions for the Konno-Sanuki equation. Moreover, we present these solutions through graphics.

1. Introduction

Nonlinear Partial Differential Equations (NPDEs) and their solutions can describe many natural phenomena. Important methods exist to seek soliton solutions, such as the inverse scattering method, Hirota bilinear method, Bäcklund transformations, among others. The eigenvalue problem associated is frequently used on the underlying structure of some solutions methods, for example, the inverse scattering method. One can explain solution solutions methods by using algebraic or geometric perspectives.

Sasaki has shown that nonlinear equations illustrated by the inverse scattering method describe pseudo spherical surfaces, presented some geometric interpretations of Bäcklund transformation and conservation laws to solitons equations [17]. On the other hand, Chern and Tenenblat [8] introduced the Bäcklund transformations for the Korteweg-de Vries (KdV), modified Korteweg-de Vries (mKdV) and sine-Gordon equations through a systematic geometric method, thus enabling a more organized study for the pseudospherical equations.

In [13] Konno et al obtained the equation of the motion for the nonlinear lattice under the influence of the weak dislocation potential,

$$z_{xt} + \frac{3}{2}z_x^2 z_{xx} + z_{xxx} - \alpha \sin(z) = 0,$$

well known as Konno-Sanuki equation, furthermore, they discovered that the equation considered has N-kink solution. In [12] the Bäcklund transformations and non-linear superposition formula for the Konno-Sanuki equation were obtained by Konno and Sanuki.

The breather solution is a particular 2-soliton solution, which is a periodic in time, spatially localized real function. The breather solutions were previously studied for the sine-Gordon [4], mKdV equation [1, 2], and Gardner equation [3]. The wobble solution for the sine-Gordon equation was first obtained by Segur [18]. Kälberman [11] gave an analytical form of this solution using the inverse scattering method. Ferreira et al [9] obtained the wobble through the Hirota method and they showed that the wobble was a 3-soliton solution, where two solitons combined to form the breather and the third soliton as a kink. More recently, Cuenda et al [7] constructed the wobble solution for the sine-Gordon equation via Bäcklund transformation; they found the parameters of the transformation corresponding to the Bianchi diagram to obtain the wobble as a special case of a 3-soliton solution.

Our work aims to obtain the breather and wobble solution for the Konno-Sanuki equation via Bäcklund transformation. The paper is organized as follows. Section 2, we collect some preliminaries on differential equations that describe

pseudospherical surfaces. We observe that the Konno-Sanuki equation is a known example that belongs to this class and use this fact to present its Bäcklund transformation and non-linear superposition formula. Section 3, we construct the breather and wobble exact solutions for the Konno-Sanuki equation through Bäcklund transformation and illustrate these solutions through graphics. Finally, in Section 4, the conclusions are presented.

2. Preliminaries

In this section, we collect some preliminaries on differential equations that describe pseudospherical surfaces. Moreover, we observe that the Konno-Sanuki equation is a known example that belongs to this class and use this fact to present its Bäcklund transformation and non-linear superposition formula.

2.1 Equations which describe pseudospherical surfaces

If (M, g) is a 2-dimensional Riemannian manifold and $\{\omega_1, \omega_2\}$ is a co-frame, dual to an orthonormal frame $\{e_1, e_2\}$, then $g = \omega_1^2 + \omega_2^2$ and ω_i satisfy the structure equations: $d\omega_1 = \omega_3 \wedge \omega_2$ and $d\omega_2 = \omega_1 \wedge \omega_3$, where ω_3 denotes the connection form defined as $\omega_3(e_i) = d\omega_i(e_1, e_2)$. The Gaussian curvature of M is the function K such that $d\omega_3 = -K\omega_1 \wedge \omega_2$.

A k -th order differential equation \mathcal{E} , for a real-valued function $z(x, t)$, describes pseudospherical surfaces if it is equivalent to the structure equations of a surface with Gaussian curvature $K = -1$, i.e.,

$$d\omega_1 = \omega_3 \wedge \omega_2, \quad d\omega_2 = \omega_1 \wedge \omega_3, \quad d\omega_3 = \omega_1 \wedge \omega_2, \quad (2.1)$$

where $\{\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3\}$ are 1-forms

$$\omega_1 = f_{11}dx + f_{12}dt, \quad \omega_2 = f_{21}dx + f_{22}dt, \quad \omega_3 = f_{31}dx + f_{32}dt, \quad (2.2)$$

such that $\omega_1 \wedge \omega_2 \neq 0$ and f_{ij} are smooth functions of $x, t, z(x, t)$ and derivatives of $z(x, t)$ with respect to x and t .

A classical example of an equation describing pseudospherical surfaces is the Konno-Sanuki equation

$$z_{xt} = z_{xxxx} + \frac{3}{2}z_x^2 z_{xx} + \alpha \sin z, \quad (2.3)$$

which corresponds to associated 1-forms (2.2) with the f_{ij} given by

$$\begin{aligned} f_{11} &= 0, & f_{12} &= -\eta z_{xx} + \alpha \frac{\sin(z)}{\eta}, \\ f_{21} &= \eta, & f_{22} &= \frac{\eta z_x^2}{2} + \eta^3 + \alpha \frac{\cos(z)}{\eta}, \\ f_{31} &= z_x, & f_{32} &= z_{xxx} + \frac{z_x^3}{2} + \eta^2 z_x, \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

and $\alpha, \eta \in \mathbb{R} - \{0\}$.

Equations that describe pseudospherical surfaces can also be characterized in a few alternative ways. For instance, the system of equations (2.1) is equivalent to the integrability condition of the linear system

$$\begin{pmatrix} dv^1 \\ dv^2 \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \omega_2 & \omega_1 - \omega_3 \\ \omega_1 + \omega_3 & -\omega_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} v^1 \\ v^2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.5)$$

where $v^i = v^i(x, t)$. Moreover, by using the notation $V := (v^1, v^2)^T$, (2.5) can be written as the linear problem

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial x} = XV, \quad \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} = TV, \quad (2.6)$$

with X and T being the $\mathfrak{sl}(2, \mathbb{R})$ -valued smooth functions (also known as Lax pair in matrix form)

$$X = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} f_{21} & f_{11} - f_{31} \\ f_{11} + f_{31} & -f_{21} \end{pmatrix}, \quad T = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} f_{22} & f_{12} - f_{32} \\ f_{12} + f_{32} & -f_{22} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.7)$$

It is easy to show that equations (2.1) are equivalent to the integrability condition of (2.6), namely

$$\frac{\partial X}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + [X, T] = 0. \quad (2.8)$$

The condition above is usually referred to as an $\mathfrak{sl}_2(\mathbb{R})$ -valued zero-curvature representation for the differential equation \mathcal{E} . Moreover, the linear system (2.5) or (2.6) is referred to as *the linear problem associated to \mathcal{E}* .

It is this linear problem that, in some cases, is used in the construction of explicit solutions of equations describing pseudospherical surfaces, by means of the inverse scattering method [5, 6, 10].

2.2 Bäcklund transformation and superposition fórmula

To obtain the Riccati system of an equation that describe pseudospherical surfaces, it suffices to introduce the function $\Gamma = -\frac{v^2}{v^1}$ into (2.6), hence it is immediate that (2.6) reduce to

$$\begin{cases} \Gamma_x + f_{31} \frac{1+\Gamma^2}{2} + \eta\Gamma + f_{11} \frac{1-\Gamma^2}{2} = 0, \\ \Gamma_t + f_{32} \frac{1+\Gamma^2}{2} + f_{22}\Gamma + f_{12} \frac{1-\Gamma^2}{2} = 0. \end{cases} \quad (2.9)$$

By substituting (2.4) into (2.9), one can conclude that the Riccati system equation for the Konno-Sanuki equation is given by

$$\begin{cases} \Gamma_x + \frac{\bar{z}}{2}\Gamma^2 + \eta\Gamma + \frac{\bar{z}}{2} = 0, \\ \Gamma_t + \frac{1}{2} \left(z_{xxx} + \eta z_{xx} + \frac{1}{2}z_x^3 + \eta^2 z_x - \frac{\alpha \sin(z)}{\eta} \right) \Gamma^2 + \left(\frac{1}{2}\eta z_x^2 + \eta^3 + \frac{\alpha \cos(z)}{\eta} \right) \Gamma \\ + \frac{1}{2} \left(z_{xxx} - \eta z_{xx} + \frac{1}{2}z_x^3 + \eta^2 z_x + \frac{\alpha \sin(z)}{\eta} \right) = 0. \end{cases} \quad (2.10)$$

Following the Konno-Wadati procedure [14], it is easy to see that the transformation

$$\bar{\Gamma} = \frac{1}{\Gamma}, \quad \bar{z} = z + 4 \tan^{-1}(\Gamma), \quad (2.11)$$

leads to invariant (2.10) (see [16]). By solving (2.11) with respect to Γ and substituting the result in (2.10), one obtains the well-known Bäcklund transformation of the Konno-Sanuki equation, namely

$$\begin{cases} (z + \bar{z})_x = 2\eta \sin\left(\frac{\bar{z}-z}{2}\right), \\ (z - \bar{z})_t = 2 \left[z_{xxx} + \frac{\bar{z}}{2} + \eta^2 z_x + \left(\frac{\eta z_x^2}{2} + \eta^3 + \frac{\alpha \cos(z)}{\eta} \right) \sin\left(\frac{\bar{z}-z}{2}\right) + \left(\frac{\alpha \sin(z)}{\eta} - \eta z_{xx} \right) \cos\left(\frac{\bar{z}-z}{2}\right) \right], \end{cases} \quad (2.12)$$

where η represents a parameter of the transformation. This procedure to relate z and \bar{z} can be denoted by $\bar{z} = \mathbb{B}_\eta(z)$. The first equation of (2.12) coincides with the spatial part of the Bäcklund transformation of the sine-Gordon equation [8]. Therefore, the permutability theorem of the Konno-Sanuki equation is obtained in the same way of the permutability theorem of the sine-Gordon equation [15]. Hence, by considering $z_1 = \mathbb{B}_{\eta_1}(z_0)$ and $z_2 = \mathbb{B}_{\eta_2}(z_0)$, if $z_{12} = \mathbb{B}_{\eta_2}(z_1)$ and $z_{21} = \mathbb{B}_{\eta_1}(z_2)$, then $z_{12} = \mathbb{B}_{\eta_2}(\mathbb{B}_{\eta_1}(z_0)) = \mathbb{B}_{\eta_1}(\mathbb{B}_{\eta_2}(z_0))$, (see Figure 1). Moreover, z_{12} is given by

$$z_{12} = z_0 + 4 \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{\eta_1 + \eta_2}{\eta_1 - \eta_2} \tan\left(\frac{z_2 - z_1}{4}\right) \right]. \quad (2.13)$$

Figure 1: Diagrama de Bianchi

3. Breather and wobble solutions for Konno-Sanuki equation

In section, we construct the breather and wobble exact solutions for the Konno-Sanuki equation (2.3) through Bäcklund transformation (2.12) and illustrate these solutions through graphics.

3.1 Breather solution

The breather solution is a particular 2-soliton solution. However, to get this type of solution, we consider the initial solution $z_0 = 0$, and the parameters complex

conjugates with unitary norms (see Figure 1), as follows the

Theorem 3.1. The breather solution for the Konno-Sanuki equation (2.3), via Bäcklund transformations, is given by

$$z_{12} = 4 \tan^{-1} \left\{ \frac{\cos(\theta) \sin[x \sin(\theta) + t(\sin(3\theta) - \alpha \sin(\theta))]}{\sin(\theta) \cosh[x \cos(\theta) + t(\cos(3\theta) + \alpha \cos(\theta))]} \right\}, \quad (3.1)$$

where $\theta = \arg(\eta_1)$, $\theta \neq \frac{k\pi}{2}$, $k \in \mathbb{Z}$, and $\alpha \neq 0$.

Proof. Consider the particular solution of the Konno-Sanuki equation (2.3) $z_0 = 0$. Suppose $z_1 = \mathbb{B}_{\eta_1}(z_0)$ and $z_2 = \mathbb{B}_{\eta_2}(z_0)$. By using (2.12), one obtains

$$z_1 = 4 \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{\exp(\Phi_1)} \right], \quad z_2 = 4 \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{\exp(\Phi_2)} \right], \quad (3.2)$$

where $\Phi_i = \eta_i x + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\eta_i} + \eta_i^3 \right) t + k_i$ and k_i can depend on η_i , $i = 1, 2$. Take into account that $\eta = \eta_1 = \cos \theta + i \sin \theta$, $\eta_2 = \cos \theta - i \sin \theta$, $k_1 = k_2 = 0$. By introducing the function $\Phi = A(x, t) + iB(x, t)$, with

$$A(x, t) = x \cos(\theta) + t[\cos(3\theta) + \alpha \cos(\theta)], \quad B(x, t) = x \sin(\theta) + t[\sin(3\theta) - \alpha \sin(\theta)], \quad (3.3)$$

it is easy to check that $\Phi_1 = \Phi$ and $\Phi_2 = \bar{\Phi}$. Hence, by the non-linear superposition formula (2.13), one has that

$$z_{12} = 4 \tan^{-1} \left\{ \frac{\cos(\theta)}{i \sin(\theta)} \tan \left[\tan^{-1}(\exp(-\bar{\Phi})) - \tan^{-1}(\exp(-\Phi)) \right] \right\}. \quad (3.4)$$

By using the formula

$$\tan^{-1}(M) - \tan^{-1}(N) = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{M - N}{1 + MN} \right),$$

(3.4) is equivalent to

$$z_{12} = 4 \tan^{-1} \left\{ \frac{\cos(\theta) [\exp(-\bar{\Phi}) - \exp(-\Phi)]}{i \sin(\theta) [1 + \exp(-\Phi - \bar{\Phi})]} \right\}. \quad (3.5)$$

Since $\exp(-\bar{\Phi}) - \exp(-\Phi) = 2i \exp(-A) \sin(B)$, $\exp(-\Phi - \bar{\Phi}) = \exp(-2A)$ and taking into account (3.3), it follows that (3.5) reduce to (3.1). \square

Figure 2: Breather solution for Konno-Sanuki equation: $\alpha = 1/2$; $\theta = \frac{\pi}{3}$; $t = 0, 5, 10$, respectively

3.2 Wobble solution

The wobble solution is a particular 3-soliton solution. However, to get this type of solution, we consider the initial solution $z_0 = 0$, η_2 is a real parameter, and that η_1, η_3 are parameters complex conjugates with unitary norms, as follows the

Figure 3: Diagrama de Bianchi

Theorem 3.2. *The wobble solution for the Konno-Sanuki equation (2.3), via Bäcklund transformations, is given by*

$$z_{123} = 4 \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{P - Q \exp(\varphi)}{P \exp(\varphi) + Q} \right], \quad (3.6)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi &= \lambda x + \left(\lambda^3 + \frac{1}{\lambda} \right) t, \quad \lambda \in \mathbb{R}, \\ P &= \lambda \sin(2\theta) [\cos(B) + \sinh(A) \sinh(\varphi)] - (\lambda^2 + 1) \sin(\theta) \cosh(A) \cosh(\varphi), \\ Q &= (\lambda^2 - 1) \sin(B) \cos(\theta) \cosh(\varphi) + \lambda \sin(2\theta) [\sinh(A) - \cos(B) \sinh(\varphi)], \end{aligned} \quad (3.7)$$

with $\lambda \in \mathbb{R} - \{0\}$, $\theta = \arg(\eta_1)$, A, B given by (3.3), and P, Q satisfying $P^2 + Q^2 \neq 0$.

Proof. Consider the particular solution of the Konno-Sanuki equation (2.3) $z_0 = 0$ and $z_1 = \mathbb{B}_{\eta_1}(z_0)$, $z_2 = \mathbb{B}_{\eta_2}(z_0)$, $z_3 = \mathbb{B}_{\eta_3}(z_0)$. By using (2.12), one can obtains

$$z_1 = 4 \tan^{-1}(b_1), \quad z_2 = 4 \tan^{-1}(b_2), \quad z_3 = 4 \tan^{-1}(b_2), \quad (3.8)$$

with

$$b_1 = \frac{1}{\exp(\Phi_1)}, \quad b_2 = \frac{1}{\exp(\Phi_2)}, \quad b_3 = \frac{1}{\exp(\Phi_3)},$$

where $\Phi_i = \eta_i x + \left(\eta_i^3 + \frac{\alpha}{\eta_i}\right)t + k_i$ and k_i can depend on η_i , $i = 1, 2, 3$. Take into account that $\eta = \eta_1 = \cos \theta + i \sin \theta$, $\eta_2 = \lambda \in \mathbb{R}$, $\eta_3 = \cos \theta - i \sin \theta$, $k_1 = k_2 = k_3 = 0$. Hence, by the non-linear superposition formula (2.13), one gets

$$z_{12} = 4 \tan^{-1} \left(A_{12} \frac{b_2 - b_1}{1 + b_1 b_2} \right), \quad z_{23} = 4 \tan^{-1} \left(A_{23} \frac{b_3 - b_2}{1 + b_2 b_3} \right), \quad (3.9)$$

with $A_{12} = \frac{\eta_1 + \eta_2}{\eta_1 - \eta_2}$ and $A_{23} = \frac{\eta_2 + \eta_3}{\eta_2 - \eta_3}$.

According to the the permutability theorem, (see Figure 3), one has that $z_{123} = \mathbb{B}_{\eta_3}(\mathbb{B}_{\eta_1}(z_2)) = \mathbb{B}_{\eta_1}(\mathbb{B}_{\eta_3}(z_2))$. Therefore, the non-linear superposition formula (2.13) become then

$$z_{123} = z_2 + 4 \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{\eta_1 + \eta_3}{\eta_1 - \eta_3} \tan \left(\frac{z_{23} - z_{12}}{4} \right) \right].$$

Thus, by substituting (3.9), (3.8) into the above equation, it may be concluded that

$$z_{123} = 4 \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{b_2 + A_{13} \left(\frac{A_{23} b_{23} - A_{12} b_{12}}{1 + A_{23} b_{23} A_{12} b_{12}} \right)}{1 - b_2 A_{13} \left(\frac{A_{23} b_{23} - A_{12} b_{12}}{1 + A_{23} b_{23} A_{12} b_{12}} \right)} \right], \quad (3.10)$$

where $A_{ij} = \frac{\eta_i + \eta_j}{\eta_i - \eta_j}$, $b_{ij} = \frac{b_i - b_j}{1 + b_i b_j}$, with $i, j = 1, 2, 3$, $i < j$. By introducing the functions $\varphi := \Phi_2$ and $\bar{\Phi} = A(x, t) + iB(x, t)$, with $A(x, t)$, $B(x, t)$ given by (3.3), it is easy to check that $\Phi_1 = \Phi$ and $\Phi_3 = \bar{\Phi}$. Note that

$$\frac{A_{23} b_{23} - A_{12} b_{12}}{1 + A_{23} b_{23} A_{12} b_{12}} = \frac{H_1 + H_2}{Y_1 - Y_2}, \quad (3.11)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} H_1 &= (\lambda^2 - 1 - 2i\lambda \sin(\theta)) (\exp(\varphi) - \exp(\bar{\Phi})) (1 + \exp(\varphi + \bar{\Phi})), \\ H_2 &= (\lambda^2 - 1 + 2i\lambda \sin(\theta)) (\exp(\bar{\Phi}) - \exp(\varphi)) (1 + \exp(\varphi + \bar{\Phi})), \\ Y_1 &= (\lambda^2 + 1 - 2i\lambda \sin(\theta)) (1 + \exp(\varphi + \bar{\Phi})) (1 + \exp(\varphi + \bar{\Phi})), \\ Y_2 &= (\lambda^2 + 1 + 2i\lambda \sin(\theta)) (\exp(\bar{\Phi}) - \exp(\varphi)) (\exp(\varphi) - \exp(\bar{\Phi})). \end{aligned}$$

Taking into account that $\bar{\Phi} = A(x, t) + iB(x, t)$, with $A(x, t)$, $B(x, t)$ given by (3.3), one has the following expressions

$$\begin{aligned} (\exp(\varphi) - \exp(\bar{\Phi})) (1 + \exp(\varphi + \bar{\Phi})) &= 2 \exp(A + \varphi) [\cos(B) \sinh(\varphi) + i \sin(B) \cosh(\varphi) - \sinh(A)], \\ (\exp(\bar{\Phi}) - \exp(\varphi)) (1 + \exp(\varphi + \bar{\Phi})) &= 2 \exp(A + \varphi) [\sinh(A) - \cos(B) \sinh(\varphi) + i \sin(B) \cosh(\varphi)], \\ (1 + \exp(\varphi + \bar{\Phi})) (1 + \exp(\varphi + \bar{\Phi})) &= 2 \exp(A + \varphi) [\cosh(A + \varphi) + \cos(B)], \\ (\exp(\bar{\Phi}) - \exp(\varphi)) (\exp(\varphi) - \exp(\bar{\Phi})) &= 2 \exp(A + \varphi) [\cos(B) - \cosh(A - \varphi)]. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, (3.11) reduce to

$$\frac{A_{23} b_{23} - A_{12} b_{12}}{1 + A_{23} b_{23} A_{12} b_{12}} = i \frac{(\lambda^2 - 1) \sin(B) \cosh(\varphi) - 2\lambda \sin(\theta) \cos(B) \sinh(\varphi) + 2\lambda \sin(\theta) \sinh(A)}{(\lambda^2 + 1) \cosh(A) \cosh(\varphi) - 2\lambda \sinh(A) \sinh(\varphi) \cos(\theta) - 2\lambda \cos(\theta) \cos(B)}.$$

Thus, it is easy to check that (3.10) become then (3.6). \square

Figure 4: Wobble solution for Konno-Sanuki equation: $\alpha = 1$; $\theta = \frac{\pi}{3}$; $\lambda = \frac{1}{2}$; $t = 0, 10, 20$, respectively

4. Conclusions

In this paper, we have used the Bäcklund transformation to find the breather and wobble solutions for the Konno-Sanuki equation (2.3). The breather solution is represented by the formula (3.1), whereas the wobble solution is represented by relation (3.6), satisfying (3.3), and (3.7). In the construction of the breather solution, we have used the Bianchi diagram (see Figure 1) with the initial solution $z_0 = 0$, and the parameters complex conjugates with unitary norms, whereas in the construction of the wobble solution, we have used the Bianchi diagram (see Figure 3) with the initial solution $z_0 = 0$, η_2 a real parameter, and η_1, η_3 parameters complex conjugates with unitary norms. The solutions considered were represented graphically.

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